

IoT in Vehicle Presence Detection of Smart Parking System

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ABSTRACT

More and more people cluster in major cities and thus causing urbanization challenges. In this scenario, many cities are employing technologies to lessen the impact on the environment and increase productivity and efficiency to cope with the high demand. Among which, smart transportation is essential in fulfilling the mobility in the urban areas and promising to meet the increasing demand of passengers. IoT application in a smart parking system has been facilitated in various ways. To achieve its full potential, we need to understand the associated issues and principals. Therefore, this paper focus on understanding the principals within IoT, the process for the layers to function in vehicle detection, and introducing different IoT sensors empowered by different technologies, including cloud computing, big data, RFID, and WSN, that facilitate the smart parking system. After assessing the potential use cases of the IoT in the vehicle presence detection of the smart parking system, this paper will identify and discuss the benefits and challenges along with the recommendation and consideration that serve as the manual to help the industries and the governmental institutions to select appropriate sensors according to different scenarios.

INTRODUCTION

The world population is distributed unevenly and highly concentrated in urban areas causing urbanization problems [19]. Besides, there is only a limited amount of parking facilitates provided for the citizens resulting in various parking problems such as illegal parking, traffic safety issue, and energy waste. Therefore, it encourages the government to develop a smart parking system so as to make good use of the existing parking utilities to meet the high demand of citizen needs. Along with the rapid development of the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, and big data, it helps the traditional parking system become smarter and move towards the Mobility as a Service goal [12] to achieve a sustainable transportation society.

LITERATURE SURVEY

Akyildiz, I. F., Melodia, T., & Chowdhury, K. R. (2007). A survey on wireless multimedia sensor networks. *Computer Networks*, 51(4), 921-960. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2006.10.002

The availability of low-cost hardware such as CMOS cameras and microphones has fostered the development of Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks (WMSNs), i.e., networks of wirelessly interconnected devices that are able to ubiquitously retrieve

multimedia content such as video and audio streams, still images, and scalar sensor data from the environment. In this paper, the state of the art in algorithms, protocols, and hardware for wireless multimedia sensor networks is surveyed, and open research issues are discussed in detail. Architectures for WMSNs are explored, along with their advantages and drawbacks. Currently off-the-shelf hardware as well as available research prototypes for WMSNs are listed and classified. Existing solutions and open research issues at the application, transport, network, link, and physical layers of the communication protocol stack are investigated, along with possible cross-layer synergies and optimizations. Wireless sensor networks (WSN) [22] have drawn the attention of the research community in the last few years, driven by a wealth of theoretical and practical challenges. This growing interest can be largely attributed to new applications enabled by large-scale networks of small devices capable of harvesting information from the physical environment, performing simple processing on the extracted data and transmitting it to remote locations. Significant results in this area over the last few years have ushered in a surge of civil and military applications. As of today, most deployed wireless sensor networks measure scalar physical phenomena like temperature, pressure, humidity, or location of objects. In general, most of the applications have low bandwidth demands, and are usually delay tolerant. More recently, the availability of inexpensive hardware such as CMOS cameras and microphones that are able to ubiquitously capture multimedia content from the environment has fostered the development of Wireless Multimedia Sensor Networks (WMSNs) [54,90], i.e., networks of

wirelessly interconnected devices that allow retrieving video and audio streams, still images, and scalar sensor data. With rapid improvements and miniaturization in hardware, a single sensor device can be equipped with audio and visual information collection modules.

Atzori, L., Iera, A., & Morabito, G. (2010). The Internet of Things: A survey. Computer Networks, 54(15), 2787-2805. doi:10.1016/j.comnet.2010.05.010.

This paper addresses the Internet of Things. Main enabling factor of this promising paradigm is the integration of several technologies and communications solutions. Identification and tracking technologies, wired and wireless sensor and actuator networks, enhanced communication protocols (shared with the Next Generation Internet), and distributed intelligence for smart objects are just the most relevant. As one can easily imagine, any serious contribution to the advance of the Internet of Things must necessarily be the result of synergetic activities conducted in different fields of knowledge, such as telecommunications, informatics, electronics and social science. In such a complex scenario, this survey is directed to those who want to approach this complex discipline and contribute to its development. Different visions of this Internet of Things paradigm are reported and enabling technologies reviewed. What emerges is that still major issues shall be faced by the research community. The most relevant among them are addressed in details. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a novel paradigm that is rapidly gaining ground in the scenario of modern wireless telecommunications. The basic idea of this concept is the pervasive presence around us of a variety of things or

objects - such as Radio Frequency IDentification (RFID) tags, sensors, actuators, mobile phones, etc. - which, through unique addressing schemes, are able to interact with each other and cooperate with their neighbors to reach common goals [1]. Unquestionably, the main strength of the IoT idea is the high impact it will have on several aspects of everyday-life and behavior of potential users. From the point of view of a private user, the most obvious effects of the IoT introduction will be visible in both working and domestic fields. In this context, domotics, assisted living, e-health, enhanced learning are only a few examples of possible application scenarios in which the new paradigm will play a leading role in the near future. Similarly, from the perspective of business users, the most apparent consequences will be equally visible in fields such as, automation and industrial manufacturing, logistics, business/process management, intelligent transportation of people and goods. By starting from the considerations above, it should not be surprising that IoT is included by the U.S. National Intelligence Council in the list of six “Disruptive Civil Technologies” with potential impacts on U.S. national power [2]. NIC foresees that “by 2025 Internet nodes may reside in everyday things—food packages, furniture, paper documents, and more”.

Guilbert, D., Le Bastard, C., Sio-Song, I., & Yide, W. (2016). State Machine for Detecting Vehicles by Magnetometer Sensors. IEEE Sensors Journal, 16(13), 5127-5128.

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This letter presents a vehicle detection state machine for magnetometer sensors. The state machine designed by Chinrungrueng et al. [1]

for a single lane is extended to n motorway lanes with multiple lane changes. The proposed method has good performance in terms of the detection rate and false detections which are mainly due to the interference from a vehicle in an adjacent lane and lane changing. The state machine is evaluated on a real motorway and compared to industrial sensors. The understanding of road traffic congestion phenomena, the cause of accidents and the environmental aspect due to pollutants requires observations of road traffic. Many projects in Europe such as the MOCOPO project [2] are installing observation areas with different types of sensors, among which, the magnetometer is a promising new road sensor. In the MOCOPO project [2], the magnetometers are used to detect vehicles on the entry and exit ramp of a French motorway (Fig. 1), a short (about 300m) and very congested section. Wireless 3D magnetometers are specially designed to detect and reidentify vehicles in a congested situation. The sensors are sited with the commercial Sensys Network magnetometer at the entrance (Fig. 2b) or the classical Inductive Loop Detector (ILD) at the exit (Fig. 2a) for comparison purposes. In a congested situation, the detection of each vehicle is vital and the algorithm must properly segment the signal. Before undertaking the re-identification from the magnetometer, we evaluate the vehicle detection from different sensors. An experimental session with video recording takes place. The videos have been manually analyzed to give a reference database containing all vehicle which transits at the entrance/exit for each lane. The detection rate for the wireless magnetometer specially designed for the MOCOPO project [2] is considered insufficient to our purposes. In this paper, we propose a new detection

algorithm based on the state machine proposed by Chinrungrueng et al. [1]. In [1], the method was proposed for detecting vehicles in a single lane. Thus, it can not be directly applied to a multi-lane roadway. In this paper, we propose to extend this method to n motorway lanes with multiple lane changes. This complex situation can lead to false detections (FD) due to the interference from vehicles on adjacent lanes (AL) and lane changes (LC).

Ji, Z., Ganchev, I., O'Droma, M., Zhao, L., & Zhang, X. (2014). A cloud-based car parking middleware for IoT-based smart cities: Design and implementation. Sensors (Switzerland), 14(12), 22372-22393.

This paper presents the generic concept of using cloud-based intelligent car parking services in smart cities as an important application of the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm. This type of services will become an integral part of a generic IoT operational platform for smart cities due to its pure business-oriented features. A high-level view of the proposed middleware is outlined and the corresponding operational platform is illustrated. To demonstrate the provision of car parking services, based on the proposed middleware, a cloud-based intelligent car parking system for use within a university campus is described along with details of its design, implementation, and operation. A number of software solutions, including Kafka/Storm/Hbase clusters, OSGi web applications with distributed NoSQL, a rule engine, and mobile applications, are proposed to provide 'best' car parking service experience to mobile users, following the Always Best Connected and best Served

(ABC&S) paradigm. In September 2009, the European Union (EU) endorsed an Internet of Things (IoT) Strategic Research Roadmap, proposed by the Cluster of European Research Projects (CERP), named CERP-IoT [1], with the purpose of promoting, sharing and propagandizing the research projects and related research outcomes in the IoT area, especially the application of sensor technology in IoT, such as Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) [2], family-domain smart eHealth/mHealth, wearable sensing and computing, green buildings, smart homes, smart cities, etc. The report formally proposes a new communication dimension of information and communication technology (ICT)—Maintained at any time, in anyplace, by anything and anyone, providing any service within any network. In fact, this is an extension and further development (bringing it to a new level) of the “anytime-anywhere-anyhow” communication paradigm. In the public tender announcement (for a 7 billion euro annual financial support) of the EU Seventh Framework Programme (FP7), multiple projects related to IoT in nearly 20 areas were supported.

Nikitas, A., Kougiyas, I., Alyavina, E., & Njoya Tchouamou, E. (2017). How can autonomous and connected vehicles, electromobility, BRT, hyperloop, shared use mobility and mobility-as-a-service shape transport futures for the context of smart cities?. Urban Science, 1(4), 36.

A smarter transport system that caters for social, economic and environmental sustainability is arguably one of the most

critical prerequisites for creating pathways to more livable urban futures. This paper aims to provide a state-of-the-art analysis of a selection of mobility initiatives that may dictate the future of urban transportation and make cities smarter. These are mechanisms either recently introduced with encouraging uptake so far and much greater potential to contribute in a shift to a better transport paradigm or still in an embryonic stage of their development and yet to be embraced as powerful mechanisms that could change travel behaviour norms. Autonomous and connected vehicles are set to revolutionise the urban landscape by allowing machines to take over driving that for over a century has been exclusively a human activity, while electrical vehicles are already helping decarbonising the transport sector. Bus rapid transit has been steadily reinventing and rebranding conventional bus services revitalising the use of the humblest form of public transport, while hyperloop is an entirely new, disruptive, and somewhat provocative, travel mode proposition based on the use of sealed tube systems through which pods could travel free of air resistance with speeds exceeding 1000 km/h. Shared use mobility mechanisms like car-sharing, ride-sharing, ride-sourcing and public bicycles can help establishing a culture for using mobility resources on an as-needed basis, while mobility-as-a-service will take this sharing culture a step further, offering tailored mobility and trip planning packages that could entirely replace the need for privately owned modes of transport. Smart cities are the result of knowledge-intensive and creative strategies, aimed at enhancing the socio-economic, ecological, logistic and competitive performance of cities [1]. This, from a transport perspective, implies that any urban environment looking to be classified as

a smart city, should respond effectively, among others, to the dual mobility challenge, as defined by [2], of rapid urbanisation and growing traffic congestion.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Implementing IoT (Internet of Things) in the vehicle presence detection of a smart parking system can enhance efficiency, reduce congestion, and improve the overall user experience. Here's how you can integrate IoT into an existing smart parking system.

Deploy IoT-enabled sensors in parking spaces: Use sensors such as ultrasonic sensors, infrared sensors, or cameras to detect the presence of vehicles in each parking space. Connect sensors to a microcontroller or IoT gateway: The sensors should be connected to a device that can collect and transmit data. This could be a microcontroller or an IoT gateway. Choose a communication protocol: Select a communication protocol (e.g., MQTT, CoAP, HTTP) to enable the sensors to transmit data to a central server or cloud platform. Ensure secure communication: Implement security measures, such as encryption and authentication, to secure the communication between sensors and the central system. Set up a cloud platform: Use a cloud service (e.g., AWS, Azure, Google Cloud) to collect and process data from the sensors. Develop an IoT backend: Create an IoT backend that can receive, store, and analyze data from the parking sensors. This backend should also provide APIs for interaction with other components. Implement data processing algorithms: Analyze the sensor data to determine the status of each parking space (occupied or vacant). Use machine learning for predictive analysis: Implement machine learning algorithms to predict parking space availability based on historical data. Develop a user interface: Create a user-friendly interface for both administrators and end-

users to check real-time parking space availability. **Mobile app integration:** Develop a mobile application that users can use to find and reserve parking spaces, receive notifications, and make payments. **Integrate with payment systems:** Allow users to make payments for parking through the mobile app or other payment gateways. **Implement automated payment processing:** Use IoT data to automate the payment process based on the duration of parking. **Provide real-time alert** Implement a system that sends alerts to users when a parking space is about to become available or when their parking time is about to expire. Allow users to provide feedback on the parking experience, which can be used to improve the system. **Ensure scalability:** Design the system to handle a growing number of sensors and users as the smart parking system expands. **Regular maintenance and updates:** Schedule regular maintenance to ensure sensors are functioning correctly and update the system to address any security vulnerabilities or performance issues. By incorporating these elements, you can enhance the efficiency and functionality of a smart parking system using IoT technology.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The integration of IoT (Internet of Things) technology in vehicle presence detection for a Smart Parking System offers several advantages, improving efficiency, reducing traffic congestion, and enhancing overall parking management. Install IoT-enabled sensors in each parking space to detect the presence of a vehicle. Utilize various sensor technologies such as ultrasonic, infrared, or magnetic sensors. Sensors should be capable of wirelessly communicating with a central system. Establish a robust communication network, such as Wi-Fi, Zigbee, or LoRa, to connect the parking sensors with the central server. Ensure secure and reliable data

transmission between sensors and the central system. Implement a central server to collect, process, and manage data from all parking sensors. Use cloud-based solutions for scalability, data storage, and accessibility. Incorporate a database to store real-time and historical parking occupancy data. Develop a user-friendly mobile app for drivers to check parking availability in real-time. Enable features like navigation to available parking spots and mobile payments for parking fees. Provide a web-based interface for parking administrators to monitor and manage the entire parking system. Include features for analytics, reporting, and system configuration. Implement data analytics to derive insights from parking occupancy patterns. Use machine learning algorithms to predict parking space availability based on historical data, events, and trends. Collaborate with navigation system providers to integrate real-time parking data into their platforms. Enhance driver experience by providing seamless navigation to available parking spaces. Integrate a secure and automated payment system for parking fees. Utilize mobile payment options to enhance user convenience. Implement security protocols to protect the system from unauthorized access and data breaches. Ensure the confidentiality and integrity of data transmitted between sensors and the central server. Design the system to be scalable, allowing for the addition of more sensors and parking spaces. Plan for future upgrades and technology advancements in IoT and smart parking solutions. Efficient utilization of parking spaces, reducing congestion and optimizing available resources. Drivers can easily find available parking spaces, reducing search time and frustration. Parking administrators can make informed decisions based on data analytics and insights. Reduced fuel consumption and emissions due to decreased time spent searching for parking. Implementing an IoT-

based vehicle presence detection system in smart parking not only addresses current parking challenges but also contributes to creating more sustainable and efficient urban environments.

Block diagram

IR SENSOR

An [infrared sensor](#) is an electronic device, that emits in order to sense some aspects of the surroundings. An IR sensor can measure the heat of an object as well as detects the motion. These types of sensors measure only infrared radiation, rather than emitting it that is called a [passive IR sensor](#). Usually, in the infrared spectrum, all the objects radiate some form of thermal radiation. These types of radiations are invisible to our eyes, that can be detected by an infrared sensor. The emitter is simply an IR LED ([Light Emitting Diode](#))

and the detector is simply an IR photodiode that is sensitive to IR light of the same wavelength as that emitted by the IR LED. When IR light falls on the photodiode, the resistances and the output voltages will change in proportion to the magnitude of the IR light received.

Moisture Analyzers

Moisture analyzers use wavelengths which are absorbed by the moisture in the IR region. Objects are irradiated with light having these wavelengths (1.1 μm , 1.4 μm , 1.9 μm , and 2.7 μm) and also with reference wavelengths. The Lights reflected from the objects depend upon the moisture content and is detected by analyzer to measure moisture (ratio of reflected light at these wavelengths to the reflected light at reference wavelength). In GaAs PIN photodiodes, Pbs photoconductive detectors are employed in moisture analyzer circuits.

Gas Analyzers

IR sensors are used in gas analyzers which use absorption characteristics of gases in the IR region. Two types of methods are used to measure the density of gas such as dispersive and non dispersive.

Gas

Analyzer

Dispersive: An Emitted light is spectroscopically divided and their absorption characteristics are used to analyze the gas ingredients and the sample quantity.

Non dispersive: It is most commonly used method and it uses absorption characteristics without dividing the emitted light. Non dispersive types use discrete optical band pass filters, similar to sunglasses that are used for eye protection to filter out unwanted UV radiation.

This type of configuration is commonly referred to as non dispersive infrared (NDIR) technology. This type of analyzer is used for carbonated drinks, whereas non dispersive analyzer is used in most of the commercial IR instruments, for an automobile exhaust gas fuel leakages.

RFID READER

Active RFID and Passive RFID technologies, while often considered and evaluated together, are fundamentally distinct technologies with substantially different capabilities. In most cases, neither technology provides a complete solution for supply chain asset management applications. Rather, the most effective and complete supply chain solutions leverage the advantages of each technology and combine their use in complementary ways. This need for both technologies must be considered by RFID standards initiatives to effectively meet the requirements of the user community.

RFID Reader Module, are also called as interrogators. They convert radio waves

Returned from the RFID tag into a form that can be passed on to Controllers, which can

Make use of it. RFID tags and readers have to be tuned to the same frequency in order to Communicate. RFID systems use many different frequencies, but the most common and

Widely used & supported by our Reader is 125 KHz.

Functions

1. Supports reading of 64 Bit Manchester Encoded cards
2. Pins for External Antenna connection
3. Serial Interface (TTL)
4. Wiegand Interface also available

Technical Data:

- Frequency: 125 kHz
- Read Range: up to 8 cm
- Power supply: 5V DC ($\pm 5\%$)
- Current consumption max. : 60 mA
- Operating temperature: -20 ... +65° C
- Storing temperature: -40 ... +75° C
- Interface: RS232 (TTL), Wiegand and others (on Demand)
- Dimensions (l x w x h) : 36 x 18 x 10 mm

- Serial Interface Format: 9600Baud, No Parity, 8 Data bits, 1 Stop bit

Note: The TTL RS-232 Interface can not be connected directly to a PC COM port.

Therefore the signal must be converted to RS 232 level for PC connection.

This Firmware has the following Functions:

Read Tag-ID

Send Tag-ID in ASCII Format through the Serial/ Wiegand Interface.

Sequence starts with Tag ID follows from Carriage-Return/Line-Feed (0Dh 0Ah),

Example: '041201938C<CR><LF>'

Applications:

Our readers can be used for Access control, Time & Attendance, Vending machines,

Industrial and other applications where Reading the data from the Card only is required

ESP8266

The ESP8266 is a low-cost Wi-Fi microchip, with a full TCP/IP stack and microcontroller capability, produced by Espressif Systems[1]

in Shanghai, China. The chip first came to the attention of Western makers in August 2014 with the ESP-01 module, made by a third-party manufacturer Ai-Thinker. This small module allows microcontrollers to connect to a Wi-Fi network and make simple TCP/IP connections using Hayes-style commands. However, at first there was almost no English-language documentation on the chip and the commands it accepted.[2] The very low price and the fact that there were very few external components on the module, which suggested that it could eventually be very inexpensive in volume, attracted many hackers to explore the module, the chip, and the software on it, as well as to translate the Chinese documentation.[3] The ESP8285 is an ESP8266 with 1 MiB of built-in flash, allowing the building of single-chip devices capable of connecting to Wi-Fi.[4] The successors to these microcontroller chips is the ESP32 family of chips, including the pin-compatible ESP32-C3.

CONCLUSION

There are three main IoT sensors for vehicle presence detection. For city street parking lots management, it is more suitable to install a wireless magnetometer sensor due to street parking may include both indoor or outdoor spaces which require flexibility on installation location. Besides, the wireless magnetometer sensor is able to withstand normal weather condition disruption. In

addition, installing wireless magnetometer sensors only require a small inch drill hole which can be done quickly making it an ideal choice for large scale city implementation. However, an IoT smart parking system affects a whole network environment thus emphasizing the importance of personal security and privacy protection. It is the government's responsibility to establish related regulations to monitor data usage and avoid privacy issues from happening [4]. Besides, since the traffic system involves life safety issues, at the design stage, the government should take safety issues into consideration and educate the designers with effective prevention approaches such as mitigate the impact of security vulnerabilities through patching and establish vulnerability management policies to promote security updates. According to the U.S. Federal guidance report of the automotive industry aiming to improve motor vehicle cybersecurity [13], it indicated that it is important for infrastructure operators and cloud computing service providers to bear the notification obligations. In other words, the government needs to clarify the data acquisition level among different official departments and local companies and sets up proper information security management systems to undergo key actions including education and training of information security, monitor and management approach, safety inspection, and testing. IoT realizes the vision of connecting and communicating with individuals through computing and analyzing a vast amount of information sources. However, to successfully adopt new technology requires a proper framework and clear understanding of the potential challenges and associated issues.

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